

Synthesis of *p*-Camphorene

O. P. VIG and G. L. KAD*

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

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p-Camphorene is synthesised by the application of Wittig reaction with methylenetriphenylphosphorane on 1(4-methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-(5-methyl-4-hex-1-ene)cyclohex-1-ene (5), the cardinal intermediate, which was procured by the formation of β -ketosulphoxide and then its subsequent alkylation with 1-bromo-3-methyl-2-butene of the compound 1(4-methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-carbomethoxycyclohex-1-ene (3). The alkylated material was submitted to reductive cleavage with aluminium amalgam in aqueous THF at 65° to furnish 5.

p-Camphorene, a monocyclic diterpene hydrocarbon, was first found in the higher boiling fraction of camphor oil¹. Since then it has been isolated from a number of oils, such as volatile oil of *Dacrydium biforme*², Japanese tall oil³ and oil of hops⁴. Semmler and Jonas⁵ showed it to be identical with dimyrecene⁶. The characteristic structural features of this diterpene possessing structure (1) is the presence of a methylene and two isopropylidene groupings alongwith a unsubstituted double bond in the specific positions within the cyclohexane ring. Literature does not record any direct and clean synthesis of this hydrocarbon.

Here, we report a facile and unambiguous synthesis of *p*-camphorene, making use of β -ketosulphoxide as the cardinal intermediate. The sequence of reactions employed in accomplishing the synthesis is depicted in Scheme 1.

The starting material, 1(4-methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-

cyno-cyclohex-1-ene (2), was procured according to the procedure laid down in the literature⁹. The compound 2 on alcoholysis⁹ provided 1(4-methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-carbomethoxy-cyclohex-1-ene (3) in 80% yield. The resulting ester was converted into 1(4-methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-(1-oxo-2-methylsulphinyl-ethyl)cyclohex-1-ene (4) by making use of methylsulphinyl-carbanion (obtained from equimolar quantities of sodium hydride and dimethyl sulphoxide)¹⁰.

Alkylation of the β -keto sulphoxide (4) with 1-bromo-3-methyl-2-butene in dry dimethylformamide employing sodium hydride as a base¹¹ resulted in the corresponding alkylation product which was not isolated. This, upon reductive cleavage with aluminium amalgam¹⁰ in aqueous THF afforded the ketone, 1(4-methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-(5-methyl-4-en-1-oxyl)cyclohex-1-ene (5) in 57% yield after chromatographic purification. This ketone was submitted to Wittig reaction with methylenetriphenylphosphorane according to the procedure of Corey *et al.*¹². The resulting product was chromatographed over neutral alumina and subsequently distilled under vacuum to afford 1 in 74% yield, identified by comparison of its ir spectral data with those reported for the natural compound in the literature⁴.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. Ir spectra of the films were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer having sodium chloride optics.

1(4-Methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-carbomethoxy-cyclohex-1-ene (3): A slow stream of hydrogen chloride gas was bubbled into a mixture of the solution of 2 (10 g) in methanol (26.3 ml) and water (2 ml).

The resulting heat of solution caused the solvent to reflux. After the temperature had subsided (15 min), the reaction mixture was treated with water (4.7 ml), warmed on a steam-bath for 20 min and poured into an excess of cold water. The solution was extracted with solvent ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution, saturated brine solution and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was expelled and the residue was distilled under vacuum to afford 1(4-methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-carbomethoxy-cyclohex-1-ene (3; 9.4 g, 80%), b.p. 130-32°/4 mm (Found: C, 75.23; H, 9.72. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 75.67; H, 9.91%); η_D^{25} 1.4740; ν_{max} 1745 (ester), 835 and 810 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

1(4-Methyl-3-pentenyl)-4-(1-oxo-2-methylsulphinylethyl)cyclohex-1-ene (4): In a three-necked flask, equipped with rubber stopper, a magnetic stirrer and a three-way stop cock, sodium hydride (3.9 g, 50%) was washed with n-hexane to remove the mineral oil. After replacing the air in the apparatus by nitrogen, DMSO (40 ml) was added via syringe. The reaction mixture was heated at 75-80° until the evolution of hydrogen ceased (30 min). To methylsulphinyl carbanion thus formed, was added an equal volume of dry THF (40 ml) and the contents were cooled in ice-bath, followed by dropwise addition with string of the ester (3; 9.0 g) over a period of several minutes. After stirring for 1 h more at room temperature, the reaction mixture was poured into cold water (200 ml), acidified at lower temperature with calculated quantity of hydrochloric acid (10.5 ml) and thoroughly extracted with chloroform. The organic extract was washed with water and dried (anhydrous CaCl_2). Solvent evaporation, followed by vacuum distillation afforded semi-solid β -ketosulphoxide (4; 6.0 g, 65%), b.p. 180-90°/4 mm. However, all attempts to crystallise it proved unsuccessful (Found: C, 67.32; H, 8.78; S, 11.80. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires: C, 67.15; H, 8.95; S, 11.94%); ν_{max} 1695 (carbonyl), 1010-40 (sulphinyl), 825 and 780 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

1(4-Methyl-3-pentenyl)-4(5-methyl-4-hex-1-ene)-cyclohex-1-ene (5): Dry dimethylformamide (40 ml) was added to sodium hydride (0.36 g, 50%) under an atmosphere of nitrogen. The resulting slurry was cooled, stirred and the solution of 4 (4.0 g) in dry dimethylformamide (20 ml) was added to it slowly so as to keep the ensuing reaction under control. Stirring was continued at room temperature till the conversion of 4 into the anion was complete (cessation of hydrogen evolution). At this stage, the reaction mixture was again cooled and 1-bromo-3-methyl-2-butene (2.75 g) (prepared by the addition of hydrobromic acid to isoprene) added to it dropwise. After continuing the stirring for another 30 min at room temperature, the contents were put into cold water (100 ml) and

extracted with chloroform. The organic layer was washed with saturated brine solution and dried (anhydrous CaCl_2). The residue, left after the removal of the solvent from the dried organic phase, was placed under vacuum for 1 h to yield the alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (which was not isolated).

The above alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (4.0 g) was dissolved in aqueous tetrahydrofuran (240 ml, 10%). The solution was taken in a three-necked flask provided with a reflux condenser and a mechanical stirrer. Freshly prepared aluminium amalgam (obtained by immersing 3.3 g aluminium in 2% mercuric chloride for 15 s) was added to this well stirred solution in the form of small pieces. The contents were then refluxed at 65° for 90 min. Thereafter, the reaction mixture was filtered and the residual solid washed well with tetrahydrofuran. The combined filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent expelled. The residual oil was chromatographed over alumina (50 g) with benzene-petroleum ether (1:4) as eluent and carefully fractionated under vacuum to obtain the desired ketone (5, 57% with respect to 4), b.p. 140-142°/4 mm (Found: C, 82.76; H, 10.42. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}$ requires: C, 83.21; H, 10.95%); η_D^{25} 1.4355; tlc showed a single spot (solvent system: benzene: n-hexane; 1:1); ν_{max} 1710 (carbonyl), 835, 815 and 795 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

p-Camphorene (1): Sodium hydride (0.48 g, 50%) was washed with n-hexane to remove the mineral oil and freshly distilled dimethyl sulphoxide (6 ml) was added to it under nitrogen atmosphere. The contents were heated with stirring (75-80°) until hydrogen gas ceased to evolve (nearly 45 min). The resulting solution was cooled in an ice-water-bath and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (4.05 g) dissolved in dimethyl sulphoxide (12 ml) was introduced to it to furnish a dark red solution of the desired phosphorane. After stirring the above mixture at room temperature for 10 min, the ketone (5; 2.74 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) was added and the stirring was continued for 2 h. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature and heated at 50° for 1 h with stirring. The contents were poured into cold water and extracted with petroleum ether (4 × 25 ml). The combined extract was washed with water and dried. The solvent having been evaporated, the residue was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina (20 g) using petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°, 80 ml) as eluent. It was followed by distillation under reduced pressure to obtain 1 (2.0 g, 74%), b.p. 172-74°/5 mm (Found: C, 87.93; H, 12.07. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{32}$ requires: C, 88.23; H, 11.77%); η_D^{25} 1.4894; ν_{max} 3070, 1650, 892 (methylene), 835, 815 (trisubstituted double bond), 2900, 1450, 1380, 1120, 925 and 750 cm^{-1} .

VIG & KAD : SYNTHESIS OF *p*-CAMPHORENE

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